

Investigation of potential risk factors for African Swine Fever incursion in commercial pig herds in Lithuania

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Abstract

Since the first cases of African swine fever (ASF) in wild boar in Lithuania reported in 2014, this disease became endemic in wild boar and poses a constant threat to domestic pig population in Lithuania as well as other countries around the world. Several risk factors have been found associated with the increased risk of ASF virus (ASFV) incursion to domestic pig farms and the number of outbreaks of ASF in domestic pig farms in European countries showed a clear seasonal increase in the summer period. However, the defined causes of ASF outbreaks in domestic pigs have been very rarely determined. Therefore, for the investigation of potential risk factors for ASF incursion to commercial pig farms, a matched by herd size prospective case-control study was implemented in Lithuania from 2021 to 2024. For case and control farms a questionnaire was used to collect information on potential risk factors and in both farms an entomological study to investigate the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of ASFV was performed. During the study only 3 ASF outbreaks in commercial farms met the inclusion criteria and were investigated with the 6 control farms. Due to the insufficient number of ASF case farms during the study period no conclusions could be made regarding risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial pig farms in Lithuania. During the study in total 1692 *Culicoides* spp. individuals were collected and tested using RT-PCR for ASF virus DNA, however no stable flies *Stomoxys calcitrans* were trapped. Due to high Ct number (>30) in positive insect samples no virus isolation was attempted. The results from entomological investigations showed that biting midges *Culicoides* spp. contain ASFV DNA in both ASF affected case farms and ASF non-affected control pig farms. This suggests that even biting midges *Culicoides* spp. could potentially play a role in ASF virus transmission, but its importance still must be investigated further.

Keywords: African swine fever, outbreak, pig farms, risk factors, vectors, Lithuania

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Acknowledgements: authors wish to thank all pig farm owners for collaboration in this study and Andrius Petrašiūnas from Vilnius University Life Sciences Centre, Institute of Biosciences, Department of Zoology, Vilnius, Lithuania for help in entomological study.

Summary

Several risk factors have been found associated with the increased risk of African swine fever (ASF) incursion to domestic pig farms and the number of outbreaks of ASF in domestic pig farms in European countries showed a clear seasonal increase in summer period. The most frequently reported risk factors for ASF are the presence of ASF in wild boars, low levels of biosecurity, presence of infected farms in the neighborhood, visitors, swill feeding, feed matrices contaminated with ASF virus (ASFV) and blood-feeding arthropods. However, the defined causes of ASF outbreaks in domestic pigs have been very rarely determined. Therefore, for the investigation of potential risk factors for ASF incursion to commercial pig farms with more than 9 pigs, a matched by herd size prospective case-control study was implemented Lithuania from 2021 to 2024. For case and control farms a questionnaire was used to collect information on potential risk factors and in both farms an entomological study to investigate the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of ASF was performed. No ASF outbreaks in domestic pig farms occurred in 2021 in Lithuania. During the 2022 and 2023 study years only 3 ASF outbreaks in commercial farms met the inclusion criteria and accordingly 6 control farms were investigated. Due to the insufficient number of ASF case farms during the study period no conclusions could be made regarding risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial pig farms in Lithuania. For the entomological study in total 1692 *Culicoides* female individuals were collected for ASF virus DNA detection. Twelve species and 6 species complexes of *Culicoides* spp. were identified. All collected biting midges (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae) have been tested in pools of maximum 10 individuals by RT-PCR for ASFV. During the study no stable flies *Stomoxys calcitrans* were trapped for testing, most likely due to unfavorable meteorological conditions for insects and short duration of trapping. The results from entomological investigations showed that biting midges *Culicoides* spp. contain ASF virus DNA in both ASF affected case farms and ASF non-affected control pig farms. This suggests that even biting midges could potentially play a role of ASFV transmission to pig farms, their role in the transmission of the virus should be investigated further.

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1 Introduction

Since the introduction of African swine fever in Georgia in 2007 it has been spreading among wild boar and domestic pigs on the European continent. The first cases of African swine fever (ASF) in wild boar in Lithuania reported in January 2014 and presently the disease became endemic in wild boar and poses a constant threat to domestic pig population in Lithuania (Mačiulskis et al., 2020). In Lithuania ASF has been reported yearly with the highest number of ASF outbreaks in domestic pigs in 2018 (51 outbreak), following a decrease with nineteen outbreaks in 2019 (ADIS, 2021). Up to date several risk factors have been found associated with the increased risk of ASF incursion to domestic pig farms in Europe and the most frequently reported are the presence of ASF in wild boars, low levels of biosecurity, presence of infected farms in the neighborhood, visitors, swill feeding, feed matrices contaminated with ASFV and blood-feeding arthropods and socioeconomic factors (Olesen et al., 2020; Balmoş et al., 2021; Boklund et al., 2020; EFSA, 2022; Malakauskas et al. 2022). Furthermore, seasonality in numbers of outbreaks of ASF in domestic pig farms showed a clear summer peak (EFSA 2018a, 2020), however, it has not yet been possible to fully explain the difference in seasonality between wild boar and domestic pigs. Further, despite the increasing knowledge on epidemiology, control, and prevention of ASFV in domestic pigs and wild boar the defined cause of ASF outbreak in domestic pigs has been very rarely determined. Therefore, the present study aimed to investigate potential risk factors for ASF incursion in domestic pig herds and to investigate the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever virus in Lithuania.

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor

This contract was awarded by EFSA to:

Contractor: State Food and Veterinary Service of the Republic of Lithuania (SFVS) Official Registration No: 188601279 Siesikų Street 19, 07170 Vilnius, Lithuania

Contract title: TITLE — Support to the Veterinary Services of Lithuania to investigate potential risk factors for African Swine Fever (ASF) incursion in commercial pig herds.

Contract number: GP/EFSA/ALPHA/2021/05

1.2 Interpretation of the Terms of Reference

The following objectives were established for the study:

1. To investigate potential risk factors for ASF incursion into commercial domestic pig farms in Lithuania.
2. To investigate the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever virus to domestic pig farms.

2 Data and methodologies

2.1.1 Data collection

To ensure harmonization with other projects, pig population data were submitted to EFSA according to the population data model defined within the SIGMA project (EFSA, 2018b). As soon as an outbreak was confirmed a case farm ID was submitted to EFSA for random selection of control farms, using a random number algorithm, matched on county. From the list of eligible control farms, the first two on the list were used to call for the consent to participate in the survey and to get an update on the actual number of pigs at the time of the outbreak.

2.1.2 Investigation of potential risk factors for ASF incursion in domestic pig herds

For the investigation of potential risk factors for ASF incursion to commercial pig farms, a matched prospective case-control design was used from May 2021 to May of 2024. For the study purposes commercial pig farms were defined as farms where pigs are bred for commercial purposes. During 2021-2022 only commercial pig farms of 30 or more pigs were included however, due to very few ASF outbreaks in eligible commercial farms, in 2023 farms with 10 and more pigs bred for commercial purposes were also included in the study. This was done to increase study power as the number of ASF outbreaks has been considerably lower than estimated. For each outbreak farm, two matched control farms were randomly selected, matched by herd size (i.e. 10-29; 30-199; 200-1000; >1000) and a county in Lithuania. If a control farm was not available in the same county it was selected from a neighboring county.

For case and control farms a questionnaire was used to collect information on potential risk factors (Annex 1). Case farms were investigated as soon as possible but no later than 48 hours after confirmation of ASF on a farm, the two control farms within one week after confirmation of the case farm. All collected data were entered into the EU Survey for further analysis.

2.1.3 Entomological survey to identify vector species possibly involved with the transmission of African swine fever virus

The entomological sampling was performed in conjunction with the visits on the case and control farms for the questionnaire surveys. On the case farms, traps were placed, preferably before the animals are culled, but maximum 36 hours after culling of the last animals. Traps in the corresponding control farms were placed within a week after the confirmation on the case farm. Insect sampling on the farms was carried out only once per farm for 24 hours in each farm.

For the study purposes stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) and biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.) were targeted. For stable flies (*Stomoxys* spp.) translucent sticky traps were used (EFSA 2017). On each farm 2 traps were placed outside the pig shed in distance of minimum 15 meters from each at 1.6 m height. Traps were deployed for the whole duration of daylight. All insects were kept in cool (+4°C) and moved to -80°C after arriving to the lab and kept at this temperature until morphological identification and testing for ASFV DNA presence performed.

For biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.) trapping BG-Pro traps (Biogents) with UV light (the same as CDC trap) were used (Medlock et al. 2018). Two traps were placed outside the building at a height of 1.5 to 2 m from the ground and protected from wind, rain, and contaminating

lights. The collections have been done during the night. Traps were switched on 1h before sunset and switched off 1h after sunrise. Samples were collected in dry containers and, after collection stored as quickly as possible at -80°C , which will allow both the identification of *Culicoides* spp. (morphologically and molecularly), further virus isolation (Medlock et al. 2018) and blood meal source identification.

Vector identification

Stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) were identified according (Patra et al., 2018). Identification of biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.) was based on morphology (metric traits, non-metric traits, wing pattern) using The Interactive Identification Key for Culicoides (IIKC) (Mathieu et al. 2012). In case of uncertainty, identification was done by using PCR-based methods, primers LCO1490 and HCO2198 (Folmer et al., 1994) and analysis of Cytochrome c oxidase subunit I sequences, which are used as barcoding for many insect species.

Detection of ASFV DNA in vector samples

Prior to DNA extraction, pools of insects were made. Each pool referred always only to arthropods belonging to the same species, collected on the same site and at the same sampling event. All collected biting midges (Diptera: *Ceratopogonidae*) have been tested in pools of maximum 10 individual biting midges. Before pooling, each individual biting midge was cut into two longitudinal halves, hence two identical aliquots were obtained from each group of pooled insects. The first pool has been used for detection of ASF virus DNA and blood meal identification via PCR, and the second pool was kept at -80°C and in the case the first pool is PCR positive for later submission for virus isolation. All insects, those that are engorged insects with blood meal and without were chosen for diagnostic testing.

Extraction of DNA from all pooled samples of the collected biting midges was done using QIAamp® DNA Micro Kit (QIAGEN). The QIAamp DNA Micro Kit uses well-established technology for purification of genomic and mitochondrial DNA from small sample volumes or sizes. The procedure is suitable for a wide range of sample materials such as small volumes of blood, blood cards and small tissue samples.

For identification of the ASFV DNA by Real Time PCR in insect tissues the VetMAX African Swine Fever Virus Detection Kit (Appliedbiosystems) was used. This Duplex real-time PCR kit targets the p72 gene and an internal control, respectively according to SOP Identification of the ASFV DNA by Real Time PCR based on the ASF EURL SOPs. The VetMAX™ African Swine Fever Virus detection kit fulfills all the validation criteria of PCR characteristics and complete method, as required by the NF U47-600-2 standard. Internal positive control was added to each sample and control at the lysis step of the DNA extraction procedure. It served as a control for the DNA purification process, and it was used to monitor the presence of PCR inhibitors. Samples with Ct values of <35 were considered positive, Ct >40 negative, and Ct from 35 to 40 doubtful. Virus isolation was considered only for PCR positive samples with Ct value below 30.

Assessment/Results

During 2021-2024, there were 3 ASF outbreak farms and 6 control farms involved in the study. However, in 2021 there were no ASF outbreaks in commercial farms which would meet the study criteria. In 2022 there were 2 ASF outbreaks (in July and August) and in 2023 there was one outbreak (in July) included in the study (Figure 1). The first case farm was in category of 200-1000 pigs and the second in more than 1000 pigs per farm in 2022, and the remaining case farm in category of 10-29 pigs per farm in 2023. Two case farms were in Marijampole county (2022 and 2023) and one in Utena county (2022) (Figure 2). The epidemiological investigations of ASF case farms have been done within 48 hours, the investigation of control farms was conducted within 2-13 days. The agreement to visit the control farms was reached within several days, however the actual visit of two control farms had to be postponed for some additional days due to the owner's busy schedule or production events on a farm. Due to the very limited number of case and control farms in this study no conclusions could be made regarding risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial pig farms in Lithuania.

Figure 1. Case and control pig farms included in the African swine fever study in Lithuania during 2022-2023. Red color indicates year 2022, red triangles indicate case farms, red circles - control farms; Brown color indicates year 2023, brown triangle indicates case farm, brown circles - control farms.

Figure 2. Counties where African swine fever outbreaks in commercial pig farms and control farms were located in Lithuania during 2022-2023.

During 2022-2023 for the entomological study in total 1692 female *Culicoides* individuals from nine pig farms were collected. Only on one control farm traps were placed after one week after the case farm was confirmed, because after preliminary agreement on the placement of traps it took an additional week to finalize the placement. Only 10 insects, preliminary identified as stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*), were collected on sticky traps, however after identification none were confirmed as *Stomoxys calcitrans*. This could be due to the very low seasonal activity and unfavorable meteorological conditions for *Stomoxys calcitrans* at the time of the ASF outbreaks. Our previous studies have shown that for this species, activity when *Stomoxys calcitrans* was caught by Nzi traps, lasted from the end of May to late autumn however, several peaks of activity were obvious: the first weeks of June and July, the next at the beginning of September, and the last at the end of October (Turčinavičienė et al., 2021). The time of the outbreaks in this study did not coincide with the periods of previously observed peaks, additionally the previous study used different type of traps and placed traps for a week, compared to sticky traps and 24 hours of placement in the present study. The last outbreak in 2022 was in the end of August and control farms were sampled in the first days of September, however the meteorological conditions (very windy day and cold night, 5-8 °C) during the trapping were unfavorable for any insect activity and therefore only few biting midges and few *Musca* spp. were caught in total. Among the collected *Culicoides* spp. biting midges of 13 species and 6 species complexes were identified (Figure 3). The two species, *C. riethi* and *C. salinarius*, to our knowledge have not been recorded previously in Lithuania. However, it is not surprising to find these species in Lithuania as previous studies (Pakalniškis et al., 2006) have not investigated the immediate farm surroundings and both newly detected *Culicoides* species are distributed in Europe where the specific conditions required for larval development exist. It was noted that *C. riethi* larvae develop in water bodies characterized by an extremely low pH and a high concentration of sulphates (Romiti et al., 2021) and larvae

of *C. salinarius* can develop in saline waters (Gutsevich, 1973). Although, it was not investigated, such conditions likely could have occurred in Lithuania.

Figure 3. Species composition of *Culicoides* biting midges catches in pig farms in Lithuania 2022-2023.

During the study 118 pools of *Culicoides* spp. from the case farms and 110 pools from the control farms were examined by RT-PCR. For the first ASF outbreak in 2022 only one pool out of 38 from insects collected on the outbreak farm was positive for ASF DNA and one was with doubtful testing result. In each of the two control farms of this outbreak one pool (N=7 for the first control and N=41 for the second control) was found doubtful for ASF DNA. For the second ASF outbreak 5 pools out of 47 were found with doubtful results for the case farm and all pools (N= 3 for each farm) from the control farms were negative for ASF DNA. None of insect pools (N=33) from the third outbreak farm were positive for ASF DNA, but one positive pool and 4 doubtful pools (N=28 in total) were detected from the first control farm, and 8 pools (N=27 in total) with doubtful results were found on the second control farm. No virus isolation was performed as none of the positive samples had Ct value below 30.

After species identification *C. punctatus* s.l. has been shown as the dominant species in pig farms, and this suggests that this species is widespread in regions where collections were made. Only this species was positive for ASFV DNA in the case farm. In control farms dominant species was *C. punctatus* s.l. as well, but several other species (*C. circumscriptus*, *C. pallidicornis*, *C. kibunensis*, *C. obsoletus/scoticus/chiopterus*) were positive for ASFV DNA as well.

3 Conclusion

Due to the insufficient number of ASF case farms in Lithuania during the study period no conclusions could be made regarding risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial pig farms in Lithuania. The results from entomological investigations showed that biting midges *Culicoides* spp. contain ASF DNA in both ASF affected case farms and ASF non-affected control pig farms. This suggests that even biting midges *Culicoides* spp. could potentially play a role in ASF virus transmission, but its importance still must be investigated further.

4 Recommendations

Further large-scale studies are needed to elucidate possible risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial pig farms and the role of insects in the spread of African swine fever. As ASF DNA has been also previously found in insects, more efforts should be made to determine if such insects contain an infective ASF virus. Biosecurity, including insect nets, remains as the one of the available measures for ASF prevention in pig farms.

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Abbreviations

ASF	African swine fever
ASFV	African swine fever virus
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
RT-PCR	Real Time polymerase chain reaction

Annex A – Questionnaire on ASF in domestic pig farms in Romania/Lithuania/Poland

Questionnaire on ASF in domestic pig farms in Romania/Lithuania/Poland

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this survey is to collect epidemiological data as well as any available information on the development of ASF in Romania/Poland/Lithuania to:

- Perform an analysis of the temporal and spatial patterns of ASF in domestic pigs, and
- Analyse the risk factors involved in the occurrence of ASF virus in **commercial pig farms**

INSTRUCTIONS

Please, carefully read the instructions before completing the questionnaire.

- A commercial pig farm is a holding where pigs are bred for commercial purposes. For this study, **only commercial pig farms of 30 or more pigs will be included.**
- Case (outbreak) farms will be farms where ASF has been confirmed.
- A list of 10 randomly selected control farms from the same county as case farm will be provided, matching on size (e.g. 30-200; 201-1000; >1000) each case farm. If a holding is selected as control holding, but preventive culling has been applied, or the control holding is suspected or has become (in the meanwhile) positive, please go to the next control holding on the list provided.
- High Risk Period (HRP) is defined as the length of time between possible introduction date and detection of the disease, during which no control measures have yet been implemented and disease continues to spread. To harmonize answers, we have arbitrarily defined a time lapse of 6 weeks.
- Note that you will be asked to provide the GPS location of the holding. Please, be equipped with a device that can retrieve this information (e.g. smartphone), or, if not possible to use a device, complete this information before the visit.

FIRST PART: TO BE FILLED IN BEFORE THE VISIT of the HOLDING by the team member appointed to perform the survey

* 1. Please, select your country:

- Lithuania
- Poland
- Romania

* 2. Full name of team member appointed to carry out the questionnaire:

* 3. Email address:

Information about the holding

* 4. Holding ID:

* 5. Disease status of pig herd

- Outbreak
- Control

* 6. If outbreak holding, kindly provide the date of ASF confirmation:

* 7. If control holding, kindly provide:

a. the case farm holding ID to which this control farm was associated

b. the date of the outbreak

* 8. Poland county (NUTS3) code:

SECOND PART: to be filled in DURING the visit

11. GPS coordinates (WGS84 coordinate system):

Example: Barcelona (Spain) has coordinates 41.403380 latitude, 2.174030 longitude

* Latitude

* Longitude

* 12. Date of the visit

Holding animals' information

* 13. Kindly provide the total number of pigs in the holding (all animals including sucklers):

* 14. Please, specify the number of each kind of pigs in the holding:

Small sucklers in farrowing boxes/pens (please provide an estimate if the exact number is not known):

* Weaned piglets (7-30 kg = piglets before they go to fattening)

* Breeding sows:

* Breeding boars:

* Fattening male pigs:

* Fattening female pigs:

* Fattening pigs (when sex is unknown):

* 15. Where are the pigs slaughtered?

- On the holding (including own slaughterhouse)
- In a contracted slaughterhouse
- No slaughter on farm (for example if they are all sold)

* 16. Does the farm owner have other pig farms?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, which is their holding ID?

* 17. Are there other animal species bred/kept IN the pig holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Bovine
- Ovine
- Caprine
- Poultry
- Horses
- Pets (dogs, cats)
- Rabbits
- Other
- No other species

* If other, please, specify which and the number of each species:

* 18. Are there other animal species bred/kept OUTSIDE the pig holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Bovine
- Ovine
- Caprine
- Poultry
- Horses
- Pets (dogs, cats)
- Rabbits

- Other
- No other species

Wild boar information

* 19. Have you, or somebody else, ever seen a wild boar or other pigs roaming near (i.e. within 100 m) your farm?

- Yes
- No

* 20. Did you ever notice crossbred pigs born in your holding?

- Yes
- No

* 21. Have you, or somebody else, ever seen a wild boar body / body remains in the vicinity of your farm?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, at what distance?

[please provide an estimate if you don't know the exact distance]

m

* 22. Could a wild boar access the feed storage?

- Yes
- No

* 23. Could a wild boar access the bedding storage?

- Yes
- No

* 24. Are there any attractive feed sources for wild boar (e.g. crops or trees) around/near (i.e. within 100 m) the holding?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify which type of feed source:

- Maize
- Fruit trees
- Oak trees
- Other

* 25. Is there any wild boar baiting or feeding site in the surroundings (i.e. within 100 m) of the farm (even if forbidden)?

- Yes
- No

Feed and drinking water

* 26. What type of feed is given on your holding?

Investigation of ASF risk factors in Lithuania

More than one answer is possible

- Industrial compound feed: mesh
- Hay
- Industrial compound feed: pellets
- Fresh grass
- Wet feed (for example buttermilk, whey)
- On-farm milling and mixture
- Cereals (including cereals used in your own on-farm milling and mixtures)

* Please specify the municipality/ies where cereals have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* Please specify the municipality/ies where hay have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* Please specify the municipality/ies where grass have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* 27. Are there any signs of use of kitchen waste (to be answered by official vet)?

- Yes
- No

* 28. Do you feed kitchen waste (to be answered by farmer)?

- Yes
- No

* 29. What kind of drinking water is provided to the animals?

More than one answer is possible

- Fountain water (pumped from groundwater)
- Rain water stored in holding's own reservoir (e.g. tank, container, basin...)
- River/lake water
- Tap water (drinking / cleaning / disinfected water)

* If option 2 is selected, do wild boars have access to water reservoir?

- Yes
- No

Biosecurity

* 30. Did pigs have access to any type of outdoor areas on your holding within the last 6 weeks before the confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

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- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify the type of outdoor farm:

- Pigs have access to an outdoor area in forest, woodlands on agriculture land or pastures (see Figure 1 below)
- Pigs have access to an outdoor area on farm premises (adjacent to farm buildings) (see Figure 2 below)

Type of outdoor farm:

1

2

* 31. Did you introduce agriculture machinery and/or equipment potentially in contact with pigs within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

More than one answer is possible

- Yes, purchased new from dealer
- Yes, second hand or borrowed
- No

* 33. Is there a point of disinfection for the wheels at the entrance of the holding?

- Yes
- No

* 34. How many visits of professionals on the holding (number of people entering the farm for professional reasons) occurred on average on a daily basis within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

Private veterinarians:

* Official veterinarians:

* Farm workers:

* Consultants (industry reps...):

* Suppliers of farm utensils/feed:

* Live animal traders:

* Others:

* If OTHERS, please specify which:

* 36. How many visitors (number of people belonging to family, friends, students, entering the farm for personal reasons) entered the holding on average on a daily basis within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

 visitors

* 37. Was there any unusual event within the 6 weeks before the confirmation of the outbreak on the case farm/on the control farm corresponding to the case farm in case the interview is on a control farm?

More than one answer is possible

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- Construction work new building
- Change of staff
- Family/social event
- Break in biosecurity routine
- Other
- No
- I don't know

* If OTHER, please specify which:

* 38. What kind of bedding is used in the sheds?

More than one answer is possible

- Straw
- Wood chips
- Sawdust
- None
- Other

* If OTHER, please specify which:

* 39. Is the holding fenced to avoid contact with wild animals (e.g. wild boar, wolves, foxes, jackals...)?

- Yes
- No

* What type of fence?

- Double fence
- Solid single fence
- Single fence

* 41. Is manure from other holdings spread on neighbouring farmlands situated directly next to your stables (< 500 meters)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 42. Were NEW pigs and/or piglets introduced or purchased in the establishment within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm?

- Yes
- No

* 43. Were pigs sold from the establishment within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the

case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

- Yes
- No

* 44. Were there any possible contacts with case farms within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm? (e.g. natural mount, artificial insemination, shared material/objects/vehicles, external visitors, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure/I do not know

* If yes, please specify the type of contact (e.g. vehicles, people, equipment...):

* 45. Does anyone among the workers of your holding carry out any outdoor activity (in wild boar habitat)?

More than one answer is possible

- Work (forest management, agricultural activities, bee-keeping, ...)
- Leisure (hiking, mountain climbing, mountain biking, bird watching...)
- Hunting
- None of the above I don't know
- Other

* If other, please specify which:

* 46 . Are the workers allowed to bring their own food in the holding?

- Yes
- No

* 47. Does anyone among the workers of your holding have contact to pigs on other farms or in their private life (including other premises owned by you)?

- Yes
- No

* 48. Can carcasses be collected by the rendering company from the public road, without entering to the premises?

- Yes
- No

* 49. Can the feed be delivered from the public road without entering the premises?

- Yes
- No

* 50. How are pigs loaded, when they leave for selling or slaughter?

- Truck enters farm and pigs can possibly return to shed from the truck
- Truck enters farm and pigs cannot return to shed from the truck
- Truck does not enter farm and pigs cannot return to shed

* 51. Are pig pens accessible to visitors and workers only through the locker room?

- Yes
- No

* 52. Is there a rodent control management plan implemented?

- Yes
- No

* 53. Are there intact insect nets placed in front of the air intakes and the windows in the sheds?

- Yes, on all air intakes and the windows
- Yes, but not on all air intakes and the windows
- No

* If yes, please provide the approximate mesh diameter:

mm

* 54. Do you apply insecticide in or around your pig shed?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, when was an insecticide last applied? (number of days since last application)

days

* 55. What product is used for disinfection of baths/ boot washers/stables at the holding?

Name of commercial product

* 56. Is a quarantine period respected if new pigs arrive or are purchased in your holding?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, how many days?

days

* 57. Is the procedure all-in/all-out for all pigs on farm implemented?

- Yes
- No

Seasonality

- * 58. Do you share any crop harvesting machinery with other pig farmers?
 - Yes
 - No
- * 59. Is there a change in diet of the pigs over summer?
 - Yes
 - No
- * If yes, please specify ...

Open question for case farms

- * 60. Is there any other potential risk factor that we did not inquire about, that you consider the possible reason of introduction of the virus on your farm?

Background Documents

[Data Protection Note \[ENG\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[LT\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[PL\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[RO\]](#)